

**INFLUENCE OF INLET GUIDE VANE PATTERN ON AEROMECHANICS AND
AERODYNAMIC MISTUNING IN A TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR**

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ABSTRACT

Non-axisymmetric pattern of inlet guide vane stagger angles are applied for aerodynamic mistuning of a transonic compressor blisk rotor. The experimental investigation is carried out at the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt, using a 1.5-stage modern front stage compressor and extensive instrumentation for aerodynamic and aeroelastic measurements. A systematic study of asymmetric configurations indicates an effective mistuning application with certain limitations and design challenges. Preventing the formation of circumferentially propagating coherent aerodynamic waves and lock-in with blisk modes is the key mistuning mechanism. It is based on radial and circumferential flow redistribution throughout the compressor and especially varying operating conditions during one revolution of the rotor. Consequently, aerodynamic pre-stall disturbances, fundamental to convective NSV, rise and decay, depending on the relative position with respect to the inflow asymmetry. These effects are influenced by the degree of circumferential stagger angle variation and full-annulus schedule of the variable inlet guide vanes. This study investigates the overall aeroelastic behavior, especially during transient operation at the stability limit, as well as mistuning capabilities and limitations, focusing on trends during part speed operating conditions, as these are crucial for flexible engine operability.

Keywords: transonic axial compressor, experiment, aeroelasticity, NSV, mistuning

NOMENCLATURE

1T	First torsional blade eigenmode
5HP	Five-hole probe
am	Aerodynamic mistuning
BTT	Blade tip timing
FSI	Fluid-structure-interaction
ME	Measurement section
N(100)	Rotor speed in percentage design speed
NSV	Non-synchronous vibration
RI	Rotor inlet
SG	Strain gauges
t, TA, TB	Transition section
VIGV	Variable inlet guide vane
WPT	Wall pressure transducer
α	Vane stagger angle
$\Delta\alpha_{RI}$	Absolute rotor inflow angle offset
$\Delta\beta_{RI}$	Relative rotor inflow angle offset
u, u_{tip}	Rotor (tip) speed
$p_{ensemble}$	Ensemble averaged pressure
$p_{dyn,in}$	Dynamic pressure at stage inlet
$p_s, p_{s,WPT}$	Static pressure, unsteady static pressure
$p_t, p_{t,in}$	Total pressure, total pressure at stage inlet
T_t	Total temperature
ρ_{in}	Fluid density at stage inlet

1. INTRODUCTION

Future aero engine designs require novel approaches in technology to cope with the environmental challenges and related regulations regarding reduced emissions of exhaust gases and noise. Therefore, the development trends of aero engines target opportunities to increase efficiency in conjunction with reduced weight and size. The axial core compressor trends aim for lightweight designs with higher overall pressure ratios, resulting in increased aerodynamic blade loading. The related fluid-structure-interaction (FSI) of modern blisk rotors, especially in front stages, lead to a vulnerability to blade vibration. Therefore, deriving suitable countermeasures that support the avoidance of non-synchronous vibration (NSV) and flutter has been research focus for decades.

One common method is intentional mistuning, hence features with defined non-uniformities. On the one hand, mistuning can be applied to the structure, for example by varying the blade eigenfrequencies (e.g. Kielb et al. [1] and Figaschewsky et al. [2]). On the other hand, aerodynamic asymmetries can also be considered, both within the rotor (e.g. Eckici et al. [3]), e.g. by varying blade pitch or geometry, and adjacent components, e.g. eccentric tip gaps or partial casing treatments (e.g. Jüngst et al. [4] and Jüngst [5]).

In recent years, novel approaches of aerodynamic mistuning by applying large scale circumferential features have proven promising capabilities to reduce NSV. Here, especially convective NSV, introduced by Stapelfeldt and Brandstetter [8], has been research focus. Preventing circumferentially propagating coherent aerodynamic wave pattern, based on aerodynamic pre-stall disturbances in the vicinity of the operating limits, mitigates fluid-structure-interaction as well as related lock-in and amplification of convective aerodynamics and blisk vibrations.

The current investigation applies aerodynamic mistuning using different pattern of the variable inlet guide vane (VIGV). This study indicates benefits with respect to NSV mitigation and influences on performance as well as steady and unsteady aerodynamics within the compressor stage, e.g. circumferentially varying operating conditions, as presented in Franke et al. [6, 7]. Thus, the rotor encounters different loading conditions during one revolution, preventing the formation of coherent convective aerodynamic waves, able to excite and couple aeroelastically with the rotor.

Based on a systematic variation of mistuning configurations, specific measurement procedures and developed analysis methods, the circumferential variation in aerodynamics throughout the compressor stage is determined, both at steady-state and transient operating conditions. Additionally, potential limitations and drawbacks, for example impacts on forced response and adjacent stages, are investigated. The applied mis-stagger pattern of the VIGV leads to strong asymmetry in the compressor flow (i.e. pressure distribution, flow angles, mass flow), and, similar to inlet distortions or non-axisymmetric tip clearance, affects aerodynamic performance, operating range

and stability behavior as well as the impact on adjacent stages, both upstream and downstream. As the VIGV schedule is adjusted during part speed operation, the effects of non-uniformities and potential forcing have to be considered. Concerning mistuning capabilities, the VIGV mistuning is mainly aiming to suppress convective NSV. Theoretical models and simulations for different types of mistuning, as presented by Stapelfeldt and Brandstetter [9], indicate that the average decay rate of convective aerodynamic disturbances is a key influencing factor to alter the fluid-structure-coupling. Besides others, varying the full annulus VIGV schedule already provided evidence to impact the convective mechanism and related aeroelastic phenomena (compare Franke et al. [10]). Nevertheless, the mis-stagger pattern of VIGV mistuning adds a circumferential inhomogeneity, attenuating the formation of coherent waves of aerodynamic disturbances and the possibility to couple with blisk modes.

Hence, VIGV asymmetries provide great design potential for intended mistuning or even in-service reactive mistuning, and might be a feasible countermeasure for NSV as well as potentially also flutter or aero acoustic challenges in axial compressors. First results of the underlying aerodynamics and aeromechanics have been investigated and presented in [6, 7].

The goal of this research is to derive a comprehensive understanding of underlying phenomena, focusing on transient effects during stall inception, and aeroelastic effects. This includes trends due to different VIGV asymmetry pattern and schedules, especially at part speed operating conditions.

2. METHODOLOGIES

The experimental investigations were conducted at the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt test facility at Technical University of Darmstadt, as shown in Figure 1. The modular design of the rig and compressor allows quick and easy variations of test objectives, and extensive steady and time-resolving instrumentation enables aerodynamic and aeroelastic measurements.

FIGURE 1: TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR DARMSTADT

2.1 Test Rig and Objectives

The test rig is operated in an open-loop cycle, using ambient air, and driven by an 800 kW electric drive with a gearbox, enabling shaft speeds of more than 20,000 rpm. The compressor represents a modern high pressure front stage compressor in a 1.5-stage configuration with variable inlet guide vanes and a blisk rotor, designed by Rolls-Royce Deutschland Ltd. & Co KG. This research compressor was used in several experimental and numerical investigations, for example Brandstetter et al. [11], Möller and Schiffer [12] and Franke et al. [13]. At the stability limit, first torsional (1T) non-synchronous blade vibration have been reported for various operating conditions.

Different non-axisymmetric inlet guide vane configurations are applied to enable large scale circumferential flow variation for aerodynamic mistuning. The vanes are arranged in circumferential stagger angle pattern, as schematically illustrated in Figure 2. It includes configurations with 180 degree sectors and a systematic stagger variation (a) as well as different circumferential extend (c), relative/ alternating positions (d) and transition sectors (b). The circumferential variation is given in percentage VIGV schedule range of the nominal configuration at design speed. The annulus mean stagger angle and schedule of the mistuning configuration matches the nominal. The table in Figure 2 summarizes the test objectives with related abbreviations and color scheme.

FIGURE 2: TEST CONFIGURATIONS AND APPLICATION

2.2 Instrumentation and Experimental Procedures

The test facility and compressor core are equipped with different measurement systems within several measurement sections, as illustrated in Figure 3. To monitor the compressor operation and determine performance parameters, this includes total pressure and total temperature as well as torque and speed measurements. For detailed aerodynamic investigations, traversable five-hole probes (5HP) are mounted in the rotor inlet and outlet section. Various circumferentially distributed static pressure taps are applied throughout the entire compressor.

For unsteady aerodynamic and blade vibration measurements, time-resolving instrumentation is used (Fig. 3). The blade vibrations are measured via strain gauges (SG) on the rotor blades, and supplemented by a tip timing system (BTT) in the casing. The unsteady flow phenomena at the blade tip region are resolved by a variety of time-resolved wall pressure transducers (WPT). Up to 70 sensors are flush-mounted in the rotor casing and arranged in axial arrays as well as at several circumferential positions. The axial array covers the whole axial blade chord length and an upstream extension, in order to resolve secondary flow features. The circumferentially distributed sensors are located at the blade leading edge, enabling analysis of convective aerodynamics and structural vibration.

The conducted analysis is based on comprehensive experimental investigations, including steady-state and transient tests along the entire operating range. Measurements are performed at multiple constant speed lines with a variety of related VIGV schedules. For stall inception and stability behavior assessment, the compressor can be continuously throttled to operate along a certain speed line. Additionally, acceleration and deceleration maneuvers are performed to enable investigations of forced response phenomena.

FIGURE 3: INSTRUMENTATION

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The variety of test objectives in conjunction with the extensive instrumentation and measurements enable a detailed analysis of steady and unsteady aerodynamics as well as the aeroelastic behavior. The feasibility of VIGV asymmetries for intended aerodynamic mistuning in transonic compressors has been presented in Franke et al. [6, 7].

3.1 Trends in Performance and Steady Aerodynamics

Since the aerodynamic boundary conditions of the rotor vary due to the VIGV pattern, the aeroelastic advantages are accompanied by impacts on aerodynamics and performance. The overall operability of the compressor stage can be maintained, even though efficiency penalties are evident, depending on the VIGV pattern and degree of stagger variation. Radial and circumferential flow redistribution has been identified throughout the compressor stage, also affecting adjacent stages upstream and downstream. Due to circumferential rotor inlet flow variations of up to 20% of the annulus average, the rotor encounters circumference-dependent operating conditions, resulting in varying aerodynamics and work input during one revolution, as presented in [7].

In order to globally summarize and illustrate the effect schematically, velocity triangles of the rotor can be derived for the non-axisymmetric flow conditions, as shown in Figure 4. This form of illustration is based on Hall et al. [14], presenting results for non-axisymmetric flow due to inlet distortions. The black arrows illustrate the full-annulus mean flow velocity triangles upstream of the rotor for exemplary operating conditions. The blue arrows indicate the perturbation velocity, in this case at an arbitrary circumferential positions with respect to the VIGV asymmetry. The shaded areas illustrate the range of absolute and relative flow angles into the rotor, resulting in combined axial and circumferential velocity variations around the circumference, indicated by the blue lines. At the inlet, the rotor experiences circumferential variations in both flow angle and velocity magnitude during one revolution, highlighted by the blue ellipses (schematically and not to scale). The absolute flow angle is varied by the VIGV pattern, leading to corresponding relative flow angles. This leads to strong incidence, hence loading variations during one rotor revolution. The effect on the stage aerodynamics is presented in [7].

FIGURE 4: SCHEMATIC VELOCITY TRIANGLES AT THE ROTOR DUE TO INFLOW ASYMMETRIES

3.2 Unsteady Aerodynamics and Stall Inception

The circumferential variation in operating conditions of the rotor results in clear effects with respect to the blade tip aerodynamics, most relevant for modern transonic compressor rotors. During one rotor revolution, local loading, shock position and corresponding interaction with the tip leakage flow vary periodically. As pointed out in [7], aerodynamic fluctuations, indicating aerodynamic disturbances, rise and decay according to the inflow conditions of the rotor. This phenomenon is fundamental to mitigate fluid-structure-interaction and aeroelastic lock-in. In order to investigate the effect on the convective mechanism and underlying aerodynamics, the unsteady wall pressure data is analyzed in more detail. For simplifications, the largest VIGV mis-stagger configuration, am-180x2-100 respectively, is utilized for the following analysis.

Figure 5 illustrates the instantaneous pressure field at the blade tip as well as the corresponding pressure deviations with respect to the ensemble-averaged flow field for steady-state near stall operating conditions at design speed with am-180x2-100. The circumferential variation due to the VIGV pattern is clearly visible, underlining previous findings. Low pressure regions (blue dots), visible in the pressure field and emphasized in the deviation plots, indicate aerodynamic pre-stall disturbances. These disturbances predominantly occur at annulus sections with low inlet mass flows and strong increase in positive incidence (at the transition between closed and opened VIGV at about 180°). The strong and rapid variation in incidence due to the transition from positive to negative pre-swirl seems to trigger aerodynamic disturbances. As already shown for the nominal case, e.g. [11], those pre-stall disturbances mainly propagate in the vicinity of the rotor leading edge, resulting in high unsteadiness (compare [7]). Through the sector with opened VIGV the disturbances decay, and are shifted into the passage, hence circumferential propagation across multiple rotor passages or even revolutions is diminished. For a large part of the annulus, only small unsteadiness within the passage and low shock fluctuations are present. Full-annulus propagating aerodynamic waves are not established.

In order to assess the unsteady aerodynamic behavior at the stability limit in more detail, transient stall inception maneuvers are analyzed. Figure 6 shows the circumferential unsteady pressure deviations during stall inception at design speed. The revolution-wise pressure deviations of a WPT sensor at the rotor leading edge are illustrated for 1000 revolutions prior to rotating stall (marked with revolution 0) and during stall. The time-resolved data underline the steady-state results with strong circumferential variations, depending on the local flow field during one rotor revolution. Furthermore, the revolution-wise deviations clearly indicate variations in the transient behavior, depending on the relative position to the VIGV pattern. Between 0° and 150° (sector with closed VIGV), the pressure deviations are constantly low until stall occurs. Close to the transition of closed and opened VIGV, the overall level of deviations is increased already 1000 revolutions prior to stall initiation. After the transition, deviations start at a high level, which fits to the findings at steady-state operating conditions in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5: INSTANTANEOUS WALL PRESSURE FIELD AND DEVIATION FROM ENSEMBLE AVERAGE AT N100 NS

These pressure deviations are continuously rising during stall inception. Within the sector of opened VIGV, the initiation of rising deviations varies, and is shifted closer to the onset of rotating stall. This might be a result of locally varying throttling conditions around the circumference, also affecting the transient behavior.

The time-resolved wall pressure signals of circumferentially distributed WPT sensors at the rotor leading edge are shown in Figure 7. To investigate the behavior close to the stability limit, the last 100 revolutions prior to stall are plotted. Rotating stall is clearly visible at/ after revolution 0, indicating a full-annulus propagating stall cell (compare WPT spectra in [7]). Within the sector with closed VIGV, the WPT signal prior to stall is almost clean, besides individual spikes (see markers A), and an increasing overall level of unsteadiness. Some already circumferentially propagating disturbances are evident about 30 revolutions prior to stall (marker B), resulting from larger disturbances within the opened VIGV sector. Those are damped within the closed VIGV sector. Especially after the transition of closed and opened VIGV (180° - 280°), an overall unsteadiness with strong spikes and other large scale disturbances are evident.

3.3 Aeromechanics and Mistuning Capabilities

The above mentioned circumferential variation in convective aerodynamic phenomena clearly affects the fluid-structure-interaction and corresponding vibration. Figure 8 compares the first torsional (1T) blade vibration amplitudes during stall inception at design speed of the nominal configuration and am-180x2-100.

FIGURE 6: CIRCUMFERENTIAL UNSTEADY PRESSURE DEVIATIONS DURING STALL INCEPTION AT DESIGN SPEED

The strain gauge data is normalized with the maximum value of the nominal case, and plotted for -1000 revolutions prior to and 500 revolutions after the onset of rotating stall (marked by revolution 0). At the beginning of the throttling maneuver, both configurations have a similar low vibration level. At about 500 revolutions prior to stall, the nominal case shows the onset of NSV due to an aeroelastic lock-in mechanism, as presented in [8] and [11]. The vibration amplitude continuously increases until the aerodynamic stability limit, hence rotating stall, is reached, resulting in a sudden drop of the 1T amplitudes. During rotating stall, the overall vibration level is only slightly increased at about 20% of the maximum NSV amplitudes prior to stall.

FIGURE 7: CIRCUMFERENTIAL UNSTEADY WALL PRESSURE SIGNALS AT THE ROTOR LEADING EDGE DURING STALL INCEPTION AT DESIGN SPEED

FIGURE 8: BLADE VIBRATION AMPLITUDES OF 1T MODE DURING STALL INCEPTION AT DESIGN SPEED

The configuration with VIGV asymmetry shows distinct differences. No clear onset of pre-stall vibrations, NSV respectively, is visible during transient throttling. Shortly prior to rotating stall, the amplitudes rise and stay almost constant even during rotating stall at a comparable overall level as for the nominal case. The excitation prior to stall might be triggered by the occurrence of random aerodynamic disturbances, as shown in Figure 7. Even though individual disturbances are able to propagate circumferentially along some parts of the annulus, depending on the throttling conditions, no full-annulus fluid-structure lock-in of coherent circumferential propagating aerodynamic waves with a distinct blisk mode occurs (compare spectral analysis in [7]). This mechanism is mitigated by the rise and decay of aerodynamic disturbances during one rotor revolution.

The general mechanism, fundamental to the mistuning capabilities of VIGV asymmetries, is therefore highlighted. Modern engines and compressors demand flexible and safe operation, especially during part speed off-design conditions. In order to investigate the global aeroelastics, mistuning capabilities and potential limitations, the stability behavior is analyzed throughout the entire operating range.

FIGURE 9: BLADE VIBRATION AMPLITUDES ALONG THE OPERATING RANGE

Figure 9 illustrates the 1T blade vibration amplitudes based on strain gauge measurements during stall inception at different rotor speeds and corresponding VIGV schedules. Here, only the maxima prior to stall onset (compare Figure 8) are considered to focus on pre-stall NSV. The values are averaged for different strain gauges on several blades and normalized with the maximum of all configurations and operating conditions.

The nominal case (black) shows blade vibration for several characteristics along the operating range, as already presented in [5], [10], [11] and [13]. Generally, the mistuning configurations are able to suppress NSV for most of the characteristics. Nevertheless, differences between the configurations and specific operating conditions, i.e. VIGV schedules, are evident. The effectiveness of VIGV mistuning seems to be attenuated accordingly.

For low part speed conditions without adjusted VIGV schedule (marker A), the overall low axial momentum of the flow might result in too small circumferential variations, unable to suppress the formation of coherent aerodynamic disturbances, propagating within the rotor for several revolutions. This effect is even amplified with reduced stagger angle variation of the VIGV pattern. On the one hand, this could be due to an insufficient rotor inflow redistribution, hence variation in local operating conditions and manipulation of the propagating aerodynamic pre-stall disturbances. On the other hand, the transition regions between the VIGV sectors, resulting in non-axisymmetric conditions around the circumference, could affect the aeroelastic mechanism. The configuration with smaller circumferential extent (am-090x1-25) shows similar results and trends along the operating range, providing evidence that the underlying mistuning mechanism is not limited to large scale features. Nevertheless, the VIGV schedule is still of high importance. The alternating pattern (am-090x2-25) indicates distinct differences and limitations. Especially during low part speed conditions (compare marker C), NSV cannot be suppressed, leading to similar vibration amplitudes as for the nominal case. A potential explanation could be the higher harmonic content in the pattern, as indicated in section 3.4. The behavior and explicit limitations at high power operating conditions (compare marker B) will be part of future studies.

In order to shed some light into the underlying aerodynamics of the presented global trends, the impact of different pattern and VIGV schedules on the circumferential flow variation at the rotor inlet is analyzed below, especially focusing on part speed operating conditions.

3.4 Impact of VIGV Schedule and Asymmetry Pattern

Variable inlet guide vanes in front stages of a compressor are mainly introduced to adjust the inlet flow conditions of the rotor depending on the off-design rotor speed. Therefore, distinct VIGV schedules are applied during part speed operation, and will affect the overall aerodynamics and flow redistribution due to VIGV asymmetries. As the rotor is already operating at off-design conditions, incidence and loading variations will be amplified. Furthermore, aeroelastic mechanism and mistuning capabilities will be altered, as indicated before.

FIGURE 10: STATIC PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION AT THE ROTOR INLET FOR DIFFERENT VIGV SCHEDULES

Figure 10 illustrates the circumferential static wall pressure distribution at the rotor inlet for three different VIGV settings. The pressure distribution is referred to the circumferential average, hence providing the deviations for the corresponding operating conditions in the compressor map with globally different mass flow rates due to the VIGV schedule. The static pressure differences are assumed to indicate mass flow variations with respect to the VIGV pattern. The overall trends match the detailed probe measurements, e.g. axial Mach number distribution at the rotor inlet, as presented in [7].

With increasing VIGV stagger angle (closed VIGV), the overall circumferential variation is amplified, and the circumferential extension of the transition sectors is pronounced.

This leads to enhanced rotor inflow variations, thus different loading conditions and associated effects on aerodynamic performance and aeroelastic phenomena. For example, the VIGV schedule for the N45 speed line (compare N45 IGV0, IGV1 and IGV2 in Figure 9) results in better mistuning capabilities with reduced blade vibration for increased pre-swirl (closed VIGVs). This is evident for all investigated configurations.

Typically, compressor VIGV schedules with increased pre-swirl are applied during part speed, hence supporting the aerodynamic mistuning. Nevertheless, a minimum degree of circumferential flow variation and redistribution is required to enable an effective mistuning application. The corresponding design recommendations will be derived in future studies. Besides the VIGV schedule, this is also driven by the applied pattern and degree of stagger variation of the VIGV asymmetry.

Different VIGV pattern evoke varying circumferential distributions, as shown in Figure 11. The static pressure deviation illustrates the differences in circumferential variation, depending on the degree of mistuning (similar to a VIGV schedule variation presented before), and the effect of smoothed transition. Additionally, the different circumferential pattern of the VIGV asymmetry with equal degree of stagger variation is clearly visible (compare am-180x2-25, am-090x2-25 and am-090x1-25).

FIGURE 11: STATIC PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION AT THE ROTOR INLET FOR DIFFERENT VIGV PATTERN

The configuration with a smaller circumferential extension (am-090x1-25) results in similar magnitude of circumferential variation as the equivalent stagger angle pattern with larger sectors (am-180x2-25), but with a shift due to the non-symmetric arrangement. For the configuration with four sectors (am-090x2-25), a lower overall variation and the higher harmonic shape is evident.

The shape and strength of the inlet flow variation influences the aeroelastic behavior and mistuning capabilities. As evident at marker A in Figure 9, lower circumferential flow variation due to the reduced degree of stagger angle difference of the configurations results in lower blade vibration reduction. The alternating pattern leads to smaller annulus sectors with adjusting flow conditions, hence the capability to attenuate propagating aerodynamic disturbances in distinct sectors (compare Figures 5, 6 and 7 as well as [7]) is limited.

The strong circumferential variations due to different VIGV pattern and schedules can also have an effect on the stall initiation of the rotor. On the one hand, the different local operating conditions around the annulus can trigger and also suppress the formation of stall cells. Whether stall is initiated at a distinct circumferential position with respect to the VIGV asymmetry, depending on the pattern, might also be of interest. On the other hand, partial-annulus stall might occur for certain operating conditions and pattern. As the transient behavior varies around the circumference (compare Figure 6), other pattern might also differentiate. The impact of the asymmetric inflow on the stall initiation and aerodynamically stable operating range will be part of future studies.

Additionally, the varying harmonic content of the non-uniform rotor inflow can lead to challenges with respect to low engine order excitation and resulting synchronous blade vibration due to forced response. The VIGV schedule also affects the forced response behavior, as indicated in [6].

4. CONCLUSION

In order to support advancements in compressor designs for future aero engines, understanding the mechanisms of aeroelastic phenomena, such as convective NSV, and deriving feasible countermeasures is crucial. This study investigates aerodynamic mistuning based on inlet guide vane stagger angle pattern (for patent see [15]). The experiments have been performed at the 1.5-stage Transonic Compressor Darmstadt test rig, using extensive instrumentation for aerodynamic and aeroelastic analysis.

The circumferentially asymmetric VIGV leads to non-uniform flow and redistribution throughout the compressor, as presented in Franke et al. [7]. The rotor encounters circumference-dependent operating conditions, affecting the unsteady aerodynamics at the blade tip, such as loading, shock position and formation of aerodynamic pre-stall disturbances close to the stability limit.

This results in the key mechanism of the applied aerodynamic mistuning due to VIGV asymmetries, as schematically illustrated in Figure 12:

Preventing circumferentially propagating coherent aerodynamic wave pattern based on aerodynamic pre-stall disturbances in the vicinity of the operating limits prohibits fluid-structure-interaction as well as related lock-in and amplification of convective aerodynamics and blisk vibration.

FIGURE 12: SCHEMATIC MISTUNING MECHANISM WITH VIGV ASYMMETRIES

The varying behavior during transient stall inception highlights the complex unsteady aerodynamics at the rotor tip with respect to the VIGV asymmetry. Aerodynamics and mistuning capabilities are depending on the VIGV schedule and applied pattern. Therefore, design recommendations should consider minimum circumferential flow variations throughout the operating range, in conjunction with efficiency optimized pattern at design speed conditions.

Ultimately, VIGV mistuning provides great design potential for intended and in-service reactive mistuning, and can be a feasible countermeasure for different aeroelastic instabilities.

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